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conect4children (Collaborative Network for European Clinical Trials For Children)

WP5 – Data Coordinating
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Standards

MS.38 Report on Existing Semantic Interoperability

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Introduction

The concept of semantic interoperability is becoming increasingly important in the health and research fields¹, particularly in areas where data is scarce and precious such as rare and paediatric diseases. As Information Technology plays an ever increasing role in both healthcare and clinical research, it can act as an enabler to more efficient and standardized collection of various types of data, but also, in the right circumstances, can facilitate the sharing, pooling or querying of data. Myriad software solutions exist to capture and process health and research-relevant data - to allow these disparate eHealth and eResearch systems and tools to 'speak' to one another (without the need for very time-consuming and costly human data integration activity), some degree of interoperability is necessary.

Definition

Semantic (*relating to meaning in language or logic*) **interoperability** (*ability of information systems or products to be able to work with other information systems or products without restrictions in both the present and the future*)

In terms of health data Semantic interoperability is about increasing the understanding and knowledge of diseases and health by making information and data available and interpretable by both humans and machines. Achieving semantic interoperability can bring a multitude of benefits to the healthcare field, including increased comprehension of medical terms and concepts, easy access and integration of patient records (hugely beneficial to complex and chronic diseases which require a multidisciplinary approach), a reduction in medical errors and ultimately a reduction in the cost of healthcare.

Syntactic interoperability is a related but different concept: syntactic interoperability is about the exchange of information to enable communication between systems using syntactic rules (the standards that define the structure and format of the data). In other words:

- Syntactic interoperability allows data (e.g. a file) to be exchanged between separate IT entities -for instance between computers or between health systems- meaning it can be sent and received.
- For the receiving machine/system to make sense of the data, to understand it in some way, requires a level of semantic interoperability

In many ways, it can be seen as more challenging to achieve **semantic interoperability** as this implies a mutual understanding of the meaning of data, and information in the process of communicating across systems.

¹ **Semantic Interoperability for Better Health and Safer Healthcare**

Deployment and Research Roadmap for Europe

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Why is semantic interoperability relevant to c4c?

c4c was established to overcome the multitude of barriers to the conduction of efficient paediatric clinical trials. It is well acknowledged that there are not enough medicines designed specifically for the paediatric population, and that safety and efficacy data on the paediatric population is scarce². One route to better, faster, more streamlined clinical trials in paediatric diseases is an enhanced ability for data collected in disparate systems to be able to ‘speak’ other data. This could be CRF data collected in different clinical trials by the same sponsor; or CRF data from different studies led by different sponsors/CROs; or potentially CRF data linked somehow with Real World Data, such as electronic health records (EHRs) or even registry data.

There is a general, and growing, awareness of the need to avoid siloing data and failing to optimally use and reuse data from vulnerable populations. This is particularly relevant in smaller populations, including the paediatric community but also the rare disease field. There are important overlaps between these communities: although not all paediatric conditions are rare, the *majority* are: between 50-75% of ca 6-8000 rare diseases begin in childhood³⁴, meaning that c4c must also recognize, anticipate, and manage the multiple complexities resulting from delivering trials in rare diseases⁵. Only by facilitating the pooling or exchange of data between patients with the same or comparable conditions can one reach a ‘critical mass’ and build knowledge on the condition. This is without doubt essential in the diagnosis of many paediatric rare conditions (which often requires the pooling of genomic data with deep phenotypic data, for instance, as well as potentially biosample data). However, there are also many concrete benefits to the pooling or integration of *research* data:

- Placebo or control arm data could be reused to provide baseline rates for comparisons with multiple medicinal products in subsequent trials, to reduce the need to replicate these in similar studies. Such data may also inform natural history studies of patients with the same condition.
- Data from participants exposed to active compounds could be reused or ‘pooled’ in ‘data warehouses’ to extend pharmacokinetic models
- Data could be used to replicate analyses (e.g. during regulatory review)
- Comparisons of outcomes across studies might be feasible

The activities above require standardization of data, in various ways, including semantically. One major challenge is that different systems and clinicians may use different terms to describe the same concepts. Two experts discussing a case together would know that terms like ‘microcephaly’, ‘small head’ and ‘nancephaly’ are interchangeable, and refer to essentially the same symptom; but IT systems and programmes would not know this unless programmed to know it.

Why is data sharing so important in rare diseases?

- Few patients: lack of knowledge, data silos
- Many diverse diseases, vast geographical spread
- Many RD are chronic and life limiting
- Majority have no treatment
- Patients want to share data to increase knowledge, within limits⁶

² <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4345947/>

³ Eurordis. Rare Diseases: Understanding this public health priority. Nov 2005. Available from: http://www.eurordis.org/IMG/pdf/princeps_document-EN.pdf

⁴ <https://trialsjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s13063-018-2645-0>

⁵ <https://ojrd.biomedcentral.com/track/pdf/10.1186/s13023-019-1123-4>

⁶ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/11590019_63

What applicability does Semantic Interoperability have to paediatric clinical trial data within c4c?

Two surveys were undertaken in the early stages of the c4c project to identify the current picture with regard to the use of standards, ontologies and data dictionaries. The survey was disseminated to the c4c consortium in two ways:

1. **Industry survey** – This was used to evaluate the use of data standards and data dictionaries among the 10 industry partners involved in c4c. The survey also captured the “appetite” for making data reusable. (Responses 9)
2. **Non-Industry survey** – This was sent to collect information from academic partners within c4c, who have experience of running or being involved in non-industry paediatric clinical trials. It also asked questions around the use of standards, dictionaries and other data initiatives. These are all concepts crucial to achieving semantic interoperability. (Responses 34)

These surveys showed limited awareness and use of these concepts particularly from the academic perspective.

Question: Do you use ‘document architecture’ structuring standards, such as CDISC⁷ standards, when constructing CRFs for your clinical trials?

Two thirds (6) of the companies who responded did use standards when constructing their CRFs for clinical trials and one third (3) did not.

Question: Do you use CDISC Standards specifically?

To gain a deeper understanding of which standards are being used by industry partners we expanded this question to see whether CDISC standards are being routinely used.

If the response was “We do not use CDISC standards, we use Other Standards” responders were invited to expand and provide details.

⁷ CDISC (Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium) works closely with pharmaceutical organizations around the globe to develop high-quality standards that ensure compliance with regulatory guidelines and create clarity in clinical research.

The results of this question showed 2 of the 9 companies were using CDISC standards exclusively. Where no CDISC standards exist companies take several different approaches, which include applying CDISC concepts to items, using a company standard (following the general CDISC structure), using their own standards or using other standards. One respondent also added that in rare cases they may use an alternative standard even if an applicable CDISC standard exists.

Question: Which CDISC Standards do you use?

When asked to expand on which CDISC standards are collected, the following comments were received:

- The FDA/Other regulatory mandated standards but also some other standards as well. Example is CDASH⁸.
- FDA standards and parts of the full suite of CDISC standards.

Question: Which nomenclature(s) do you capture, in terms of coding clinical conditions and comorbidities on your CRFs?

Six companies who responded 'other' mentioned MedDRA in the comment box, making it the most popular nomenclature used.

The only other suggested coding was the WHO (both WHO DD and WHO DRL)

⁸ CDASH establishes a standard way to collect data consistently across studies and sponsors so that data collection formats and structures provide clear traceability of submission data into the Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM), delivering more transparency to regulators and others who conduct data review.

Question: [Academic partners]: .Thinking about clinical trials you have participated in, are you aware of any formal standards, such as CDISC, being used when constructing CRFs for your trial?

Again there was a significant difference in the use of formal standards. 66% of Industry responders reported the use of CDISC standards. This to be expected given their mandated use by the FDA and PDMA.

Question: [Academic Partners] Which nomenclature(s) of coding clinical conditions and comorbidities have you come across in eCRFs used by clinical trials you have participated in?

There is clearly a good awareness of nomenclatures within non-industry studies and a wide range are used. Again the most well-known and well used coding was MedDRA.

Key tools, projects and ideas to promote Semantic interoperability

In exploring the importance and relevance of semantic interoperability to c4c, it is necessary to consider the wider context in which discussions are taking place and progress is being made. The following is a (non-exhaustive) summary of key projects and tools to factor-into considerations of semantic interoperability and terminology harmonization in paediatric research.

Data Standards

A typical problem of semantic interoperability in paediatric research is that the same terms are often used across studies or sites for different concepts. Equally, the same concepts are denoted by different terms⁹. Data standards offer a solution to solve this problem; by documenting agreements on representation, format, definition, structuring, use, and management of data. Standards play an important role for ensuring a common understanding of the meaning of data captured; whether that be on a CRF or during a routine hospital visit. Using data standards allows the pooling of data from disparate sources to generate new insights and knowledge about a disease or population.

CDISC Insights

The Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) is a global non-profit Standards Development Organisation. CDISC creates consensus-based data standards for clinical and

⁹ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/11590019_63

translational research using a consensus-based standards development process. Several of these standards are now required by regulators¹⁰ for electronic submissions of regulated clinical trials' data and by government funding agencies. These standards are free and open and available for download from the CDISC Website. CDISC is of particular interest to c4c as the c4c data dictionary is being built using CDISC standards (building on the existing CDISC foundational standards), and will eventually be delivered as a Paediatric Therapeutic Area User Guide (by month 72 of the project). CDISC standards are built using controlled vocabularies and as such enable the accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of data, helping the entire field of clinical research tap into—and amplify—its full value.

Controlled Terminology

A terminology (or coding system) is a formal set of controlled vocabulary in a specific domain. With a well-defined terminology, each concept in the target domain is assigned a unique code, which can be identified and processed across different medical systems in an unambiguous way. CDISC has partnered with National Cancer Institute's Enterprise Vocabulary Service (NCI EVS) to develop and support controlled terminology for all CDISC foundational standards and Therapeutic Area standards. CDISC terminology goes through an extensive process of content development and public review, with wide participation from the research and healthcare community. EVS maintains and distributes CDISC controlled terminology as part of NCI Thesaurus.¹¹

Ontologies

An ontology is a formal description of knowledge as a set of concepts within a domain and the relationships that hold between them. Given the close synergies between paediatric and rare diseases, it is important to consider the significant volume of work undertaken in the last decade in the rare disease field, in terms of agreeing ontologies to promote greater semantic interoperability of data (although the applicability of these ontologies to CRF data requires further exploration). One area of major activity concerns the **codification of diseases**; traditionally, commonly-used nosologies like ICD10 have been woefully inadequate, capturing only a few hundred of the greater than 8000 separate diseases. The Orphanet database developed its own nomenclature, the OrphaNumber, for more accurate and granular disease coding, which now exists as an ontology, the Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology, ORDO. The OrphaCode is the subject of dedicated recommendations issued by the Commission Expert Group on Rare Diseases: [Recommendation on Ways to Improve Codification for Rare Diseases in Health Information Systems \(2014\)](#). It also received the 'IRDIRC Recommended Resources' label, reserved for resources which "if used more broadly, would accelerate the pace of discoveries and translation to clinical services"¹²

Mondo disease ontology (Mondo). The mondo disease ontology aims to harmonize disease definitions across the world, by harmonizing a large number of terminological resources with a relevance to RD including Orphanet and OMIM. These efforts are essential to bring some clarity in terms of the actual number of distinct rare diseases. When such information from the major knowledge sources on rare diseases is combined algorithmically and curated within Mondo, a total of 10,393 rare disease 'leaf terms' can be identified. The majority, 6,370 rare diseases, are present in three or more resources, whereas 4,023 are unique to one source. This preliminary analysis suggests that there could be a substantially higher number of rare diseases than typically assumed at present, with obvious implications for diagnostics, drug discovery and treatment

¹⁰ <https://www.cdisc.org/resources/global-regulatory-requirements>

¹¹ <https://www.cancer.gov/research/resources/terminology/cdisc>

¹² <http://www.irdirc.org/activities/irdirc-recognized-resources/>

Mondo does not replace existing rare disease knowledge sources, but rather aids their interoperability, and computability. The end goal is to ensure that no matter which sources are used in diagnostic or mechanistic software, all rare disease patients will have access to our collective global knowledge.

This work should have a significant impact in trying to harmonize and standardize the way in which rare and paediatric diseases are described.

The Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO). The HPO is a comprehensive bioinformatic resource for the analysis of human diseases and phenotypes, and consists of a logically defined ontology of phenotypic abnormalities associated with over 7000 diseases¹³. The HPO is the clinical flagship of the Monarch Initiative (monarchinitiative.org), a much larger network of knowledge about disease biology¹⁴. Monarch embeds the HPO into a semantically unified framework of knowledge on diseases, genes, phenotypes, and model organisms with over 50,000,000 items of knowledge. Detailed descriptions of clinical abnormalities encoded using the HPO, phenotype age of onset, severity and other attributes are associated with disease entities. These phenotypic profiles are the basis for algorithmic comparison of RD patients against the HPO gold standard profiles, and are used in diagnostic tools such as the Monarch tool, Exomiser. Indeed, HPO is considered the most appropriate ontology for clinical descriptions in rare diseases, and several thousand HPO terms have already been cross-referenced with the Orphanet database (i.e. the clinical terms accompanying disease codes) resulted in harmonized phenotypic terminology. Like the ORDO and Exomiser, the HPO has received 'IRDIRC Recommended Resources' status.¹⁵

Each of these ontologies are being addressed under the European Joint Programme Rare Diseases¹⁶, funded by Horizon 2020 and national authorities. Using controlled terminology linking each data element to a shared and controlled vocabulary allows for the creation of metadata, this in turn can be linked to an ontology allowing the potential for machine readability. Using standards, ontologies and controlled terminology is therefore vital to achieve true semantic interoperability. However, as noted in the Mondo section, care must be taken to more deeply evaluate equivalency and inconsistencies across resources. Especially in RD, it is critically important to create mechanisms to align and integrate knowledge. Ontologies provide the backbone of such efforts.

Given the increasing popularity of the aforementioned ontologies to advance diagnostics, clinical care, patient registration, and rare disease research generally, any attempt to enhance the interoperability (even theoretically) of paediatric trial data and Real World Data should factor-in these key ontologies.

GriP

The Global Research in Paediatrics – GRiP Project (now closed) created a network among the main international paediatric centres – with over 1,000 structures involved in Europe, the U.S., Canada, Japan and other countries – in the form of a “Network of Excellence” to stimulate and facilitate the development and safe use of medicines for children. Their goal was achieved through a training program and integrated use of the existing research capacities, thus reducing the fragmentation and duplication of activities.

In addition to this GRiP explored ‘harmonized terminology’. This work consisted of integrating child health specific terms to a publicly accessible list of terms and concepts maintained by the National

¹³ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/30476213>

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkz997>

¹⁵ <http://www.irdirc.org/activities/irdirc-recognizedresources/>

¹⁶ <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/>

Cancer Institute of the NIH, USA.

Brokering across standards

One of the current semantic interoperability challenges, especially when reusing real world data in research, is the diversity of standards that are used by different communities and systems. Most notable is the “divide” between the standards used in healthcare and eHealth (for example, HL7, ISO and GS1 for structure, SNOMED CT, LOINC, ICD for terms) and in regulated clinical research (predominantly CDISC). The inconsistent use of the standards within each silo is also an issue. Projects that have sought to reuse EHR data for clinical trials (most notably IMI EHR4CR and EHR2EDC) have therefore needed to develop inter-standards mappings. It is not realistically possible to develop such mappings for all of the potentially tens of thousands of concepts in these standards. However it has been possible to develop reliable mappings for data sets of 100-200 data items. This can correspond to the data items within a “high value data set” i.e. a data set that can be reused in multiple contexts. The most recent and complete such mapping output has been developed by EHR2EDC. This project is currently discussing how best to:

- (a) make these mappings more widely accessible, recognizing that they will not yet be perfect or complete and need wider community experience and feedback, and therefore some maintenance resources;
- (b) contribute the stable portions of this into a standardization process, through a suitable SDO (which is currently in discussion).

c4c should consider if its data dictionary should include similar cross-standards mappings. Observational health research is the other clinical research paradigm that reuses real world data, in this case to run large scale data analyses. The IMI project EMIF was the largest scale pioneering project to develop the methods, tools and a governance framework for large scale federated architectures. A successor IMI project EHDEN is now undertaking a large scale implementation programme. Both projects have collaborated with the OHDSI community, for which data needs to be mapped to its common data model (OMOP).

c4c should consider mapping to OMOP any trial data that will be held post-trial and made available for big data research. However, it appears that this is not a medium term objective.

FAIR Data

Getting data out of existing silos is not only a matter of striving to achieve semantic interoperability, but also of making the data findable, accessible, and reusable. Together, these form the FAIR principles for research data. The principles aim at development towards data and metadata that are processable by humans and machines alike. This requires to specify not only the structures/models and terms used, but also harmonization on which data and metadata are captured. Metadata include descriptive metadata, such as author(s) of data, time of creation, and scope of a dataset; administrative data, covering technical aspects (e.g., file type), preservation aspects (e.g., a checksum or hash), and rights metadata (e.g., license information); structural metadata, describing relationships among resources; and markup languages, to annotate resources or parts thereof, or to provide layout instructions¹⁷.

It can be easily seen that the amount of metadata that can be specified about resources can be significant, and may give rise to further descriptions in order to make the metadata itself FAIR. This

¹⁷ https://groups.niso.org/apps/group_public/download.php/17446/Understanding%20Metadata.pdf

can be minimized by maximally adhering to existing standards for metadata, including for example ISO/IEC 11179 Metadata Registry, Dublin Core, and DCAT.

The GO-FAIR initiative aims to implement the FAIR data principles by offering an ecosystem of Implementation Networks (INs) that contribute to development of policies, training, and technologies for FAIR data. Within these INs, the Rare Disease IN focuses on policies, to bring together all parties involved in rare disease care and research.

Conclusion

For the c4c network, and wider paediatric research field, to achieve true Semantic Interoperability there is a need to work together on similar approaches to the problem. The various outputs from tasks 5.2 and 5.3 go some way towards helping the field achieve this.

The HPO is suitable to describe the natural history of diseases but not the results/outcome of treatments. It would possibly make sense to emphasize that making CDISC or related resources compatible with ontologies such as MONDO and HPO would improve interoperability and computability.

If the end goal of c4c is to allow data to be reuse ready, it is essential for the field to harmonize their approach. If you want to exchange data using systems, you need to ensure semantic interoperability. Within the c4c project this will involve working closely with the proof of viability studies to test the feasibility of applying the approaches described within this report, within the paediatric clinical research field.